

URL	
Title	
Authors	

For your reference, the “must-have” criteria are highlighted in **purple**.

1. Content Quality			
Indicators	Criteria	Details	
Relevance	ODL Relevant	This resource deals with online distance learning (ODL) or is applicable and transferable to ODL; it is applicable across colleges and universities.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Well-targeted Audience	This resource is intended for the target audience (faculty, staff, and administrators in higher education, etc.).	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Essentiel Content	The resource contains no unnecessary, redundant, or missing content.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Depth	Substance and Rigor	The resource offers rich, substantial, consistent, and in-depth content.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Creation Date	The resource specifies its creation or update date.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Up-to-date	In Phase	The resource is in line with current trends in education.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Consensus-based	The ideas presented are non-controversial and nuanced (as opposed to categorical or radical assertions that contradict prevailing and current schools of thought).	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Functional Links	All hyperlinks are functional and secure.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Intention	Clear Objective	The learning objective or intention of the resource is clearly stated.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Applicable	The resource is applicable and reusable within the context in which it is used.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Source Quality			
Indicators	Criteria	Details	
Credibility	Identification of Creators	The names of the creators and/or the institution to which they belong are clearly stated.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Organizational Repository	The resource is hosted on a server managed by a highly respected organization, thereby ensuring continuous access and the ability to update it (unlike a typical website).	<input type="checkbox"/>
Reliability	References Included	The resource contains references to the sources used.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Traceability of Sources	The sources used are listed in a bibliography and/or via hyperlinks.	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Language Quality			
Indicators	Criteria	Details	
Compliance with the rules	Proofreading	The rules of spelling, grammar, syntax, and punctuation are followed.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Language level	Suitable for the Target Audience	The language level is appropriate for the target audience.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Presentation Quality			
Indicators	Criteria	Details	
Clarity of information	Organization of Information	The resource is organized in a logical, hierarchical structure. Sections, headings, and subheadings enhance the clarity of the content.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Media quality	Technical Quality	The media are high-resolution, smoothly integrated, and load without delay.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Reuse	CC License or Other	The resource is licensed under a Creative Commons license (or equivalent) and allows modification (no "ND" restriction). https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/ccllicenses/	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI)			
Indicators	Criteria	Details	
Compliance with DEI rules	Gender-neutral Language	Use gender-neutral language, that is, writing that prioritizes fair representation and neutral phrasing.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Inclusive Representation	The resource illustrates diversity and avoids stereotypes or generalizations.	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Accessibility			
Indicators	Criteria	Details	
Compliance with the rules	Clear and Well-structured Texts	The resource presents the text content in a clear and well-structured manner.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Reading/Writing Assistance Tools	The textual content (e.g., text, tables) of the resource is accessible and compatible with reading and writing assistance features.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Several Ways to Present	The information is presented in various formats (including visual and audio), without any loss.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Recommendations: